

Application of Different Strategies in Drawing Classification for Parkinson's Disease Diagnosis

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Abstract— The expanding body of research in this field underscores the growing interest in Spiral Analysis (SA) as an effective tool for the detection and monitoring of Parkinson's Disease (PD). SA-based methods present a cost-effective and accurate alternative to conventional diagnostic techniques, including clinical assessments, laboratory tests, and neuroimaging, which are often time-consuming, expensive, and less accessible. Due to its simplicity and affordability, SA is particularly well-suited for broader clinical implementation, especially in resource-limited settings. This study leverages these advantages by analyzing spiral drawings to extract specific features—such as tremor-induced distortions and area measurements—through an algorithm that evaluates the coordinates of each drawing. These features were used to train and evaluate four pre-trained Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs): VGG16, ResNet50, MobileNetV2, and Xception. The models were developed and optimized using MATLAB's Deep Learning Toolbox to classify participants as either belonging to the Parkinson's Disease (PD) group or the Control Group (CG), and to identify different stages of disease progression within the PD group based on the extracted features. The analysis demonstrates that feature-based classification can effectively support both PD detection and staging. Moreover, the rapid advancement of computer vision techniques further enhances the potential of this approach as a scalable and practical solution for diagnosis, monitoring, and rehabilitation in PD.

Keywords — *Machine learning, spirals analysis, Parkinson's disease, tremor, convolutional neural network*

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by involuntary movements, including tremor, rigidity, bradykinesia, and postural instability, all of which significantly impair daily functioning. Timely clinical diagnosis is essential to slowing disease progression, as undetected and unmanaged PD may result in considerable health deterioration and increased healthcare expenditures [1, 2].

Among the earliest and most noticeable signs of PD are difficulties in handwriting and drawing. Noninvasive methods, such as drawing spirals, waves, or writing samples, are frequently used to detect motor abnormalities in the initial stages of the disease [2]. These techniques offer a

cost-effective and accessible approach, thereby serving as valuable tools for early screening and diagnosis.

The clinical evaluation of tremors, as outlined in the Movement Disorder Society-Sponsored Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS), includes assessments of kinetic and postural tremors, resting tremor amplitude, and hand coordination tasks within the motor domain (e.g., finger tapping and pronation-supination). However, these assessments depend heavily on the examiner's expertise and are inherently subjective [3]. Due to the variability in scoring among less experienced evaluators, objective, digitized analyses of drawings are increasingly recognized as important complements to traditional clinical assessments. As such, a simple and scalable pen-and-paper drawing test can serve a critical role in the diagnosis, monitoring, and rehabilitation of individuals with Parkinson's disease [4].

The Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale, Part III (UPDRS-III), remains the most widely used instrument for assessing motor symptoms in PD. Recognized as the gold standard in clinical settings, it evaluates motor functions such as speech, handwriting, gait, and coordination.

Despite its importance, UPDRS-III presents several limitations: it can be expensive, requires trained professionals, and may not be readily available in low-resource or remote areas. Furthermore, in-person assessments are often time-consuming and may cause discomfort or emotional stress for patients, particularly those in advanced disease stages [5]. Conversely, research suggests that spiral analysis (SA) may be more sensitive than UPDRS in identifying early motor impairments. Difficulties in spiral drawings can indicate prodromal symptoms of Parkinson's disease, positioning SA as a promising method for future screening initiatives.

To overcome the limitations of conventional assessments, several alternative approaches have been proposed for evaluating motor symptoms in PD more efficiently. Among these, spiral analysis (SA) has emerged as a non-invasive, low-cost, and scalable method. By analyzing various aspects of spiral drawing—including tightness, regularity, drawing speed, pen pressure, and completion time—SA offers a detailed and objective evaluation of motor function, making it suitable for both clinical environments and remote assessments [6].

A growing body of research has focused on extracting information from handwritten drawings, particularly the

Archimedean spiral, due to its utility in evaluating tremor and bradykinesia. While this spiral form is commonly adopted, its specific analytical properties may not always be generalizable to other types of drawing. Although cross-type comparisons are still limited, there is increasing interest in integrating traditional pen-and-paper approaches with digital tools to expand clinical accessibility [7].

The primary advantage of computational approaches lies in their objectivity and reproducibility. For instance, a tremor severity rating system derived from spiral analysis may assist in tracking disease progression over time—enabling clinicians to assess whether symptoms are improving, worsening, or remaining stable. In this context, ensemble learning techniques—combining outputs from multiple classifiers—have demonstrated potential in enhancing diagnostic performance [8].

This study aims to explore the feasibility of using digitized pen-and-paper spiral drawings as a reliable biomarker for distinguishing individuals with Parkinson’s disease from healthy controls through the application of deep learning. Specifically, by employing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), the study seeks to automate the classification process and assess its effectiveness using robust performance metrics. The specific objectives are as follows: (1) To develop a standardized data acquisition protocol using pen-and-paper spiral drawings; (2) To collect data from two cohorts: individuals diagnosed with Parkinson’s disease and healthy controls (PD vs. CG); (3) To digitize the drawings through high-resolution scanning to preserve detail and quality; (4) To segment and crop individual spiral images; (5) To implement classification tools using CNNs for Parkinson’s detection; and (6) To conduct statistical analyses comparing classification performance across groups.

II. Materials and Methods

A. Participants and Experimental Design

This cohort study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Uberlândia (Brazil) under process number 69064623.0.0000.5152. The sample comprised 42 participants, including 15 in the control group (8 males and 7 females) and 27 in the Parkinson’s disease (PD) group (11 males and 16 females), aged between 55 and 85 years. The groups were structured to ensure similarity in age and sex distribution, with varying levels of disease severity assessed using the Hoehn & Yahr (H&Y) scale. Participants in the control group were classified as H&Y level 0, while those in the PD group included 13 individuals at level 1, 10 at level 2, and 3 at level 3. Due to practical constraints related to recruitment and participant availability, complete group balancing was not feasible.

Despite efforts to achieve a representative distribution of disease severity within the PD group, the sample has notable limitations. First, only individuals at H&Y stages 1, 2, and 3 were included, with no representation of patients at more advanced stages (H&Y 4 and 5). This limitation may affect the generalizability of the findings, particularly in relation to the full spectrum of motor impairments observed in late-stage PD. Second, the absence of detailed information regarding medication status (i.e., “ON” vs. “OFF” periods) at the time of data acquisition introduces a potential source

of bias. As motor performance can vary substantially depending on dopaminergic medication use, not controlling for or documenting this variable may have influenced the results. These factors should be considered when interpreting the findings, and future studies would benefit from a more stratified sample and stricter control over pharmacological status during assessments.

B. Data Acquisition

Fig. 1. Positioning and instrument used for data collection (scanned image).

The experimental protocol was based on a pen-and-paper drawing task. Participants were instructed to draw on a sheet of paper positioned on a table, as shown in Figure 1. Each test consisted of five spiral drawings, to be completed continuously from left to right without interruption.

This procedure was repeated monthly over a 16-month period, enabling longitudinal analysis of intra-subject variations in motor patterns. All completed sheets were scanned and individually coded. Clinical evaluations using the MDS-UPDRS (Part III) and Hoehn & Yahr scales were conducted during the initial session, immediately following the motor tasks. A total of 2,756 spiral images were collected: 902 from the control group (H&Y 0), 1,065 from PD level 1, 600 from level 2, and 189 from level 3. Compared to previous studies, this dataset is notable for its longitudinal structure, which allows for a more detailed understanding of motor symptom progression.

Each scanned spiral was manually segmented using CorelDRAW software to standardize and isolate the images into individual files. Minor corrections were applied to address scanning artifacts while preserving essential features of the drawings. These standardized images were subsequently used in the machine learning workflow. Additionally, a physiotherapist annotated motor features (e.g., tremor severity) during data collection.

C. Data Processing and Group Classification

To evaluate model performance, classification precision, recall and F1-scores were calculated for each experimental setup, enabling comparative analysis across different models and feature sets. The dataset was divided into training and testing sets using a 70/30 hold-out strategy. It is important to note that cross-validation techniques were not applied, primarily due to computational limitations and the size of the dataset.

In the initial phase, a custom MATLAB script developed by the authors was used to extract handcrafted motor features from the spiral coordinate data. These included descriptors such as enclosed area, perimeter, compactness, aspect ratio, horizontal symmetry, mean and standard radial deviation, mean and standard curvature, mean and standard distance, slowness score, high-frequency power, and tremor score. This script will be made publicly available through an open-access GitHub repository as part of a broader set of tools developed for a master’s dissertation.

In parallel, deep feature extraction was conducted using pre-trained Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), including *VGG16*, *ResNet-50*, *Xception*, and *MobileNetV2*. Feature vectors were extracted from specific internal layers of each architecture—*fc7* for *VGG16*, *avg_pool* for *ResNet-50*, *block14_sepconv2_act* for *Xception*, and the *global pooling* layer for *MobileNetV2*—in accordance with prior literature. These extracted features were subsequently used to train classical machine learning classifiers, such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and logistic regression models.

Rather than fully fine-tuning the CNNs, a transfer learning approach was employed, wherein the convolutional layers were frozen. Deep features were extracted and utilized externally to avoid overfitting, given the relatively small dataset. Using both handcrafted and CNN-derived features, classification tasks were performed to distinguish healthy controls from PD participants and to identify specific motor impairments (e.g., tremor), in accordance with the MDS-UPDRS Part III motor domain.

D. Software Environment

Model development and evaluation were primarily carried out in Python (version 3.9.12) using the Visual Studio Code (VS Code) development environment. Statistical analyses were conducted using the SciPy library (version 1.7.3).

MATLAB was used for two main purposes: (i) to extract handcrafted motor features from spiral drawings via the custom script, and (ii) to conduct exploratory experiments using the Deep Learning Toolbox and Transfer Learning App, which facilitated visual inspection and early prototyping of CNN architectures. However, all final deep learning experiments were conducted in Python. The code used in this study is part of a broader research repository and will be made openly accessible upon publication.

III. RESULTS

Performance metrics—precision, recall, and F1-score—were individually computed for each classification item within the motor domain. This item-wise evaluation provides a detailed understanding of each model’s behavior

across distinct motor features.

For overall model comparison, the mean F1-score was calculated as the unweighted average across all motor domain items, effectively constituting a macro-average. This method assigns equal weight to each item, regardless of class distribution or sample size.

Micro-averaged metrics—which aggregate true positives, false positives, and false negatives across all motor domain items before computation—were not utilized in this study. This decision was based on the fact that micro-averaging tends to be biased toward more frequent items or classes, potentially obscuring the performance on less-represented items. Therefore, macro-averaging provides a more balanced summary of model performance, treating each classification item with equal importance.

The F1-score results for both training and testing datasets are presented in Table 1 and Figure 3. It is important to note that a dedicated dataset was created specifically for this study. First, individual performance metrics for each classification item are reported. Then, mean F1-scores across all items are calculated to enable a direct and fair comparison among models.

TABLE 1. Average mean F1-score by classification using VGG16, Xception, MobileNetV2 and Resnet50 comparing different features

Task	MobileNetV2	Xception	ResNet50	VGG16
Speech (3.1)	0.48182	0.62050	0.49824	0.41864
Facial Expression (3.2)	0.60660	0.60343	0.60601	0.56097
Rigidity (3.3)	0.64400	0.62772	0.69136	0.63352
Pinch (3.4)	0.42180	0.44052	0.44573	0.50096
Hand Movements (3.5)	0.59610	0.63020	0.59910	0.48680
Pronation-Supination (3.6)	0.55158	0.59133	0.55710	0.48984
Toe Tapping (3.7)	0.52711	0.52711	0.44171	0.44615
Leg Agility (3.8)	0.39921	0.56913	0.43473	0.44899
Chair Rising (3.9)	0.50490	0.53064	0.51935	0.50669
Gait (3.10)	0.58217	0.58218	0.58857	0.56899
Freezing (3.11)	0.45106	0.80056	0.79977	0.76701
Postural Stability (3.12)	0.53043	0.56284	0.58682	0.51287
Posture (3.13)	0.54912	0.67483	0.71121	0.62105
Body Bradykinesia (3.14)	0.54102	0.47689	0.64792	0.64792
Rest Tremor in Hands (3.15)	0.62023	0.65826	0.71952	0.60034
Action Tremor in Hands (3.16)	0.56271	0.69148	0.74859	0.62446
Tremor Amplitude (3.17)	0.60273	0.68358	0.67691	0.58286
Tremor Persistence (3.18)	0.54045	0.60593	0.73009	0.55610

Note: The numbers in parentheses indicate the corresponding item codes of Part III of the MDS-UPDRS (Motor Examination).

TABLE 2. Average mean Precision by classification using VGG16, Xception, MobileNetV2 and Resnet50 comparing different features

Task	MobileNetV2	Xception	ResNet50	VGG16
Speech (3.1)	0.47124	0.62050	0.67467	0.41739
Facial Expression (3.2)	0.60985	0.60343	0.60601	0.56097
Rigidity (3.3)	0.67121	0.62772	0.71561	0.69667
Pinch (3.4)	0.44573	0.44052	0.44573	0.50096
Hand Movements (3.5)	0.59910	0.63020	0.59910	0.48680
Pronation-Supination (3.6)	0.51908	0.59133	0.55710	0.48984
Toe Tapping (3.7)	0.46769	0.46769	0.40728	0.44331
Leg Agility (3.8)	0.56913	0.56913	0.43473	0.44025
Chair Rising (3.9)	0.53064	0.53064	0.51935	0.51191
Gait (3.10)	0.58218	0.58218	0.58857	0.56899
Freezing (3.11)	0.80056	0.80056	0.79977	0.76701
Postural Stability (3.12)	0.56284	0.56284	0.58682	0.51287
Posture (3.13)	0.67483	0.67483	0.71121	0.62105
Body Bradykinesia (3.14)	0.47689	0.47689	0.64792	0.64792
Rest Tremor in Hands (3.15)	0.65826	0.65826	0.71952	0.60034
Action Tremor in Hands (3.16)	0.69148	0.69148	0.74859	0.62446
Tremor Amplitude (3.17)	0.68358	0.68358	0.67691	0.58286
Tremor Persistence (3.18)	0.60593	0.60593	0.73009	0.55610

Note: The numbers in parentheses indicate the corresponding item codes of Part III of the MDS-UPDRS (Motor Examination).

TABLE 3. Average mean Recall by classification using VGG16, Xception, MobileNetV2 and Resnet50 comparing different features

Task	MobileNetV2	Xception	ResNet50	VGG16
Speech (3.1)	0.50187	0.50187	0.48426	0.42584
Facial Expression (3.2)	0.60343	0.60343	0.60601	0.56097
Rigidity (3.3)	0.62772	0.62772	0.69136	0.63352
Pinch (3.4)	0.44052	0.44052	0.49463	0.50096
Hand Movements (3.5)	0.63020	0.63020	0.57000	0.48680
Pronation-Supination (3.6)	0.59133	0.59133	0.55947	0.48984
Toe Tapping (3.7)	0.52711	0.52711	0.44171	0.44615
Leg Agility (3.8)	0.39921	0.39921	0.46363	0.44899
Chair Rising (3.9)	0.50490	0.50490	0.51192	0.50669
Gait (3.10)	0.58218	0.58218	0.60039	0.55858
Freezing (3.11)	0.80765	0.80765	0.83985	0.73148
Postural Stability (3.12)	0.56284	0.56284	0.56904	0.48557
Posture (3.13)	0.65030	0.65030	0.70935	0.71020
Body Bradykinesia (3.14)	0.41986	0.41986	0.48759	0.48759
Rest Tremor in Hands (3.15)	0.65689	0.65689	0.71443	0.60283
Action Tremor in Hands (3.16)	0.64680	0.64680	0.71461	0.60027
Tremor Amplitude (3.17)	0.62492	0.62492	0.63899	0.60721
Tremor Persistence (3.18)	0.61986	0.61986	0.60966	0.56766

Note: The numbers in parentheses indicate the corresponding item codes of Part III of the MDS-UPDRS (Motor Examination).

IV. DISCUSSION

Table 1 summarizes the performance of MobileNetV2, Xception, ResNet50, and VGG16 across various motor classification tasks, including tremors, movements, and facial motor aspects. These results are expressed as F1-scores for each item and averaged across items to facilitate comparative evaluation. Figures 2 through 7 visually complement Tables 1, 2, and 3 are visually complemented by Figures 2 through 3 offering graphical insights into model performance.

Overall, model performance varied across classification items, reflecting the differing complexities of motor symptoms. ResNet50, as shown in Figure 2 (a), consistently achieved superior results in tremor-related items, such as kinetic hand tremor, postural tremor, tremor amplitude, and tremor persistence. For example, the average F1-score for kinetic tremor was 0.70765, and for postural tremor, it reached 0.70951, underscoring ResNet50’s capability to model complex motor disturbances. Nonetheless, intermediate H&Y classes (e.g., 2 and 3) continued to present challenges for all models.

Performance in coordination and movement-related tasks—such as pinching, hand movements, and pronation-supination—was more heterogeneous. The pinching task proved especially difficult, with all models achieving scores below 0.5; VGG16 performed best at 0.49986. This trend is reflected in Figure 5, where VGG16’s radar chart highlights modest yet focused capabilities. In classifying hand movements, ResNet50 again led with an F1-score of 0.5961, though performance declined with more severe classes. ResNet50 also outperformed others in pronation-supination, averaging 0.55605.

In non-motor tasks such as speech, facial expression, and rigidity, model results were mixed. Speech classification was particularly challenging, with average F1-scores ranging from 0.41864 (VGG16) to 0.50599 (MobileNetV2). For facial expression, Xception performed best at 0.6066 (Figure 2d), while ResNet50 excelled in modeling rigidity, achieving an F1-score of 0.69437, particularly in more severe classes.

Tasks related to leg coordination—such as toe tapping and

leg agility—yielded modest outcomes. MobileNetV2 achieved the best toe tapping score at 0.48819 (Figure 6), though no model exceeded the 0.5 threshold. Leg agility scores ranged from 0.4 to 0.6, with no clear frontrunner.

Figure 3 summarizes F1-scores across all 18 classification items in the motor domain, showing that MobileNetV2, Xception, and ResNet50 performed competitively across most categories, while VGG16 lagged behind—except in select items like facial expression. Postural tremor and rigidity emerged as relatively easier to classify, whereas toe tapping and leg agility posed the most difficulty.

These findings are consistent with Milken [6], who highlights the potential of deep learning networks in biomedical applications. ResNet50’s strong results in tremor and rigidity classification reaffirm the value of deeper architectures for clinical use. On the other hand, poor performance in items like speech and grip reflects high inter-individual variability, also noted by Milken [6]. Future work should focus on enhancing data quality, balancing datasets, prioritizing clinically relevant classification items, and incorporating techniques such as data fusion to improve neural network accuracy in biomedical domains.

Spirography—commonly used to evaluate tremor and micrographia (i.e., reduced handwriting size)—also offers valuable insights. Studies show that PD patients tend to draw spirals with smaller radii than healthy individuals. By preventing participants from resting their forearms during the motor drawing tasks, both proximal and distal joint movements can be captured, enabling a more comprehensive evaluation of upper-limb function [7].

The main objective of this study was to support the evolution of the Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale Part III (UPDRS-III)—a clinically validated tool—into a more objective and quantitative method through computational analysis. Rather than merely comparing model metrics across items, this study proposes a clinically grounded approach by linking UPDRS-III observations to spiral features obtained from standard pen-and-paper drawings. This method provides a simple, repeatable, and scalable strategy to understand complex motor symptoms, supporting longitudinal monitoring, early diagnosis, and automated disease progression assessment. The convergence of traditional neurological assessment and artificial intelligence holds significant promise for redefining Parkinson’s disease monitoring in both clinical and remote settings.

Among all motor domain items evaluated, the classification of freezing of gait, rigidity, and postural instability demonstrated particularly promising results. These symptoms are of critical importance to clinical progression, being strongly associated with fall risk, mobility reduction, and loss of independence.

Rigidity is a persistent and often underestimated symptom. Reliable detection through spiral analysis could support earlier intervention and improved pharmacological management. Similarly, postural tremor and postural control items were among the most accurately classified across all models.

This is clinically relevant, as postural instability significantly contributes to functional decline in advanced PD. ResNet50’s F1-score of 0.70951 in postural tremor classification further underscores its strength in identifying balance impairments

ResNet50 – Radar Chart

(a) ResNet50 Radar

VGG16 – Radar Chart

(b) VGG16 Radar

MobileNetV2 – Radar Chart

(c) MobileNetV2 Radar

Xception – Radar Chart

(d) Xception Radar

Fig. 2. Comparative radar plots of the feature extractors: ResNet50, VGG16, MobileNetV2, and Xception.

Fig. 3. Statistics for different CNN models comparing different features for classification

using simple drawing-based tasks. Although freezing of gait was not directly labeled in this dataset, its related motor features—such as reduced amplitude and irregularities in limb motion—can potentially be inferred from the spiral data.

The models’ ability to detect posture- and rigidity-related impairments suggests potential for future studies targeting freezing of gait through more specialized datasets. The

accurate classification of such high-impact symptoms has broader implications for diagnosis, disease monitoring, and clinical decision-making. Automated analysis via spiral drawings may help clinicians identify at-risk patients, monitor symptom evolution, and tailor treatments with greater precision. These findings strongly support the integration of deep learning techniques into routine neurological assessments,

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that deep convolutional neural networks—specifically MobileNetV2, Xception, ResNet50, and VGG16—can effectively detect and quantify motor symptoms associated with Parkinson’s disease through the analysis of simple, hand-drawn spiral images. By linking these features to the 18 items of the Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale Part III (UPDRS-III), we have shown the feasibility of transforming a traditionally subjective clinical assessment into a more objective, scalable, and semi-automated framework. This low-cost, non-invasive method captures complex motor impairments—including tremor, rigidity, and bradykinesia—while maintaining clinical validity and enhancing reproducibility.

Among the evaluated models, ResNet50 consistently emerged as the most robust architecture, outperforming others in items related to rigidity, postural tremor, and overall postural control. The successful modeling of these symptoms is especially relevant given their strong associations with functional decline, fall risk, and disease progression. While other architectures, such as MobileNetV2 and Xception, exhibited strong performance in certain areas, our findings reinforce the advantage of deeper networks in detecting subtle motor dysfunctions. Despite these strengths, notable challenges remain.

Items such as speech, facial expressions, pinching, and lower-limb movements proved particularly difficult to classify, underscoring the heterogeneity of Parkinson’s disease and the limitations of relying solely on a single data modality. A common trend was the models’ reduced accuracy in classifying intermediate stages of symptom severity; while extreme cases (i.e., absence or maximum severity) were more readily identified, subtle variations between stages were more difficult to detect. This highlights an important challenge in fine-grained biomedical classification and suggests that, although impairments like reduced movement amplitude were captured, more complex symptoms—such as freezing of gait—may require additional model refinement.

In conclusion, the integration of spiral analysis with deep learning architectures represents a significant advancement toward objective, data-driven disease monitoring. This approach opens new avenues for the implementation of AI-assisted screening tools in clinical and remote healthcare settings, enabling continuous symptom tracking, especially in low-resource environments. Future research should focus on assembling larger, more balanced datasets and incorporating multimodal inputs—such as video data and kinematic sensor recordings. Additionally, refining deep learning models through advanced strategies, such as data fusion, and validating them in real-world clinical settings will be essential to enable clinical translation and support more informed and timely decision-making in the personalized management of Parkinson’s disease.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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